

Quality criteria for paediatric oncology centres in Switzerland: A multistakeholder consensus finding process

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Quality criteria aim to standardise and optimise the care provided to patients. Quality criteria for paediatric oncology centres exist in several countries but are missing for Switzerland. Therefore, we aimed to define quality criteria for paediatric oncology centres in Switzerland.

Methods: We conducted a three-round modified online Delphi process with 65 national stakeholders to reach a consensus on quality criteria retrieved from international sources. We asked stakeholders to decide on the relevance of categories of quality criteria (round 1), to rate (round 2) and re-rate (round 3) quality criteria regarding their relevance on a 5-point Likert scale, and to agree on a final list of quality criteria (round 3).

Results: Twenty-nine stakeholders (response rate (RR) 45 %) participated in round 1, 23 (RR 35 %) in round 2, and 24 (RR 37 %) in round 3. In round 1, ≥ 50 % of stakeholders agreed that the six categories of facilities, multidisciplinary team and other experts, supportive care, treatment, long-term care, and volume and numbers are relevant in round 1. In round 2, ≥ 75 % of stakeholders rated 61 quality criteria as "relevant" or "very relevant". In round 3, ≥ 75 % of stakeholders rated one additional quality criterion as "relevant" or "very relevant", resulting in the agreement on a list of 62 relevant quality criteria.

Conclusion: Implementing these quality criteria can improve transparency, comparability, and, therefore, the quality of care in treatment centres. These quality criteria can be piloted nationally but need to be regularly reviewed. They may also serve as a reference for other countries.

1. Introduction

The age-standardised incidence rate (ASR) of paediatric and adolescent (aged 0–19 years) cancer was 10.7 per 100'000 in 2022 globally, with the highest rates for North America (19.4), Oceania (16.8) and Europe (15.4) (International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC)). In Switzerland, the ASR was 16.4 per 100'000 in 2022, with 285 children and adolescents diagnosed with cancer (International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC)). The 5-year survival rate of Swiss children and adolescents diagnosed with cancer between 2008 and 2017 reached approximately 86 % (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2021). While these numbers are good indicators of successful diagnoses and treatments, they do not inform on the quality of care provided.

Children and adolescents diagnosed with cancer in Switzerland are treated in one of the nine specialised centres, united in the Swiss

Paediatric Oncology Group (SPOG) (Schweizerische Pädiatrische Onkologie Gruppe (SPOG)). Regulations ensure a high treatment quality within these centres, and the SPOG requires them to fulfil certain structural criteria regulated in individual contracts between the SPOG and each centre (e.g., criteria relating to a centre's responsibilities and equipment), which are regularly checked. In order to assess the quality of the centres, the SPOG Coordinating Center regularly conducts monitoring and, through external providers, audits in the SPOG centres (Swiss Paediatric Oncology Group (SPOG), 2023). Furthermore, German-speaking SPOG centres can get certified by OnkoZert from the German Cancer Society (Deutsche Krebsgesellschaft, DKG) (Deutsche Krebsgesellschaft, 2024a). So far three SPOG centres are certified (Deutsche Krebsgesellschaft, 2024b).

While the requirements of the SPOG and DKG (Deutsche Krebsgesellschaft, 2024a) continuously foster and ensure high-quality treatment

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of paediatric cancers, they focus primarily on clinical trials, treatment, and quantitative aspects (e.g., case volume, number of cases discussed in a tumour board). However, an assessment tool focusing on the holistic quality of care provided in paediatric oncology centres in Switzerland is missing.

In the European context, the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE) proposes standards of care that all paediatric oncology centres in Europe should meet (European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE) et al., 2009). These standards represent minimum requirements, and the document is currently under revision. Also the new version will consider the standard, evidence-based requirements and will therefore not cover all needs of countries with highly developed paediatric oncology centres such as Switzerland. Globally, quality criteria have been published for different countries in Europe, the US, and Canada and were recently summarised into six categories: 1) facilities and networks, 2) multidisciplinary team (MDT) and other experts, 3) supportive care, 4) treatment, 5) long-term care, and 6) volume and numbers (Schladerer et al., 2023).

Therefore, this study aimed to define quality criteria relevant for paediatric oncology centres in Switzerland by reaching a consensus among different national paediatric oncology stakeholders. An online consensus-finding process was used, complementing the previous literature review by allowing multiple stakeholders to co-create a list of quality criteria relevant for Switzerland.

2. Methods

2.1. Setting

We conducted a modified online Delphi process consisting of three iterative English-language surveys created with SurveyMonkey between February and April 2024. The ACCORD (Accurate Consensus Reporting Document) checklist was followed for transparent reporting of the study process (Gattrell et al., 2024).

2.2. Stakeholders

We sent the three survey rounds via email to 65 paediatric oncology stakeholders in Switzerland, selected via purposive sampling. Stakeholders comprised all board-certified paediatric oncologists at SPOG centres of all language regions (German, French, and Italian; $n = 54$), employees of the coordinating centre of the SPOG ($n = 3$), representatives of the largest advocacy organisation ($n = 7$) and of the survivor network ($n = 1$). We asked contacted stakeholders to forward the survey within their network.

2.3. Three online survey rounds

We asked the stakeholders to rate the relevance of quality criteria for paediatric oncology centres extracted from the international literature. We pre-selected a list of 89 quality criteria, divided into six categories, for countries with highly developed healthcare systems identified from a systematic literature review (Schladerer et al., 2023) and an international cross-sectional survey (Schladerer et al., 2024). Quality criteria not relevant in the Swiss setting (e.g., “access to a cancer registry”, as childhood cancer registration is mandatory in Switzerland by law since January 2020 (Die Bundesversammlung der Schweizerischen Eidgenossenschaft, 2016)) were excluded.

In round 1, we asked stakeholders if they consider each of the six categories identified in the literature (facilities, MDT and other experts, supportive care, treatment, long-term care, volume and numbers) relevant (answer options: yes, no, not sure) and whether an additional category should be added (Supplemental material 1). Agreement was reached if $\geq 50\%$ of stakeholders indicated that a category was relevant and the quality criteria of this category were included in round 2.

In round 2, we presented the anonymised results of round 1 (i.e., the

percentages of stakeholders who considered each category relevant) at the beginning of the survey. We then asked stakeholders to rate the relevance of the pre-selected quality criteria on a 5-point Likert scale (1: not relevant, 2: slightly relevant, 3: moderately relevant, 4: relevant, 5: very relevant, no weighting: cannot assess). Consensus was reached if $\geq 75\%$ of stakeholders answered with “relevant” or “very relevant” (“cannot assess” answers excluded from the calculation). For each category, we asked stakeholders if they would add any quality criteria (“yes” or “no”) with the option to type the suggested quality criterion (Supplemental material 1).

In round 3, we displayed the anonymised rating results of round 2 and asked stakeholders if they agree with the inclusion of the quality criteria rated as relevant or very relevant by $\geq 75\%$ of stakeholders in the previous round in a final list (“yes, I agree”, “no, I disagree” and “cannot assess”). Consensus was reached if $\geq 75\%$ of stakeholders agreed. Stakeholders could comment on their response (Supplemental material 1). We further asked stakeholders to re-rate quality criteria rated as relevant or very relevant by $< 75\%$ of stakeholders in round 2 and asked for explanations of the re-ratings. If $\geq 75\%$ of stakeholders rated a quality criterion as “relevant” or “very relevant” in round 3, we included the quality criterion.

All survey rounds were open for two weeks each. We sent reminders within each round after one week.

2.4. Free text data handling

We added newly suggested categories or quality criteria to the next survey round if they referred to the clinical aspects of quality of care and aligned with the in- and exclusion criteria of a previously conducted systematic review (Schladerer et al., 2023). We excluded quality criteria if they: i) did not refer to the quality of care of a single centre, ii) were too specific (e.g., for a diagnosis), iii) focused explicitly on adolescents and young adults, iv) were too broad and it was not clear how to measure them, v) addressed aspects covered by good clinical practice, clinical trial participation or treatment protocols, vi) addressed aspects that were under national regulation, or vii) were specific to professional or subspecialty certification (Schladerer et al., 2023).

We summarised similar comments and explanations from round 3 and excluded them if i) comments were provided together with the response “cannot assess”, ii) respondents requested the inclusion of a criterion that was listed elsewhere in the survey, or that did not align with our definition of quality criteria, iii) the comment did not add additional information (e.g., justifications for subject matters of criteria).

2.5. Data analysis

Data were analysed descriptively and graphs created using SurveyMonkey, Microsoft Excel, and SPSS.

3. Results

In round 1, 33 stakeholders responded, four of whom only indicated which group they represent, but did not rate any category. Twenty-nine stakeholders rated at least one category (response rate (RR) = 45%), of which 24 completed all questions (Table 1). For all six categories of quality criteria, consensus was reached, and categories were endorsed as relevant (Fig. 1). Stakeholders did not suggest new categories that aligned with the applied definition for quality criteria. However, they suggested two new quality criteria (“National and international collaboration”, “Diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) strategy for patients with special needs (e.g., due to migration, autism spectrum disorder/ neurodevelopment)”), which we added in categories “facilities, networks and disciplines” and “treatment” for the rating in round 2.

In round 2, 23 stakeholders participated (RR = 35%), 20 of which had participated in round 1; 21 completed all quality criteria ratings

Table 1

Number of stakeholders by groups that participated in the three consensus-finding survey rounds.

	Round 1	Round 2	Round 3
Stakeholder group (multiple answers possible)	n _{R1} (n _{dropout} R1)	n _{R2} (n _{dropout} R2)	n _{R3} (n _{dropout} R3)
Paediatric oncologists	19 (3)	15 (1)	18 (2)
Advocacy organisation representatives	7 (1)	4 (1)	4 (1)
Paediatric cancer survivor representative	1	1	-
SPOG coordinating center employees	5 (1)	3	2
Total number of stakeholders n	29 (5)	23 (2)	24 (3)
Participation in round 1	-	20 (2)	15 (1)
Participation in round 2	-	-	17 (1)

(Table 1). Sixty-one out of 91 quality criteria were rated as relevant or very relevant by ≥ 75 % of stakeholders. Thirty quality criteria were rated as “relevant” or “very relevant” by < 75 % of the stakeholders (facilities, networks and disciplines: 1 criterion, MDT and other experts: 23 criteria, supportive care: 2 criteria, treatment: 4 criteria) (Table 2, Supplemental material 2). Most stakeholders answered that they would not add quality criteria to the categories (answer “no”: facilities: 70 % (16/23), MDT and other experts: 91 % (20/22), supportive care: 91 % (20/22), treatment: 95 % (20/21), long-term care: 86 % (18/21), volume and numbers: 81 % (17/21)). Newly suggested quality criteria were not added, as suggestions did not align with the inclusion criteria.

In round 3, 24 stakeholders participated (RR = 37 %), 15 of which had participated in round 1, and 17 had participated in round 2 (Table 1). Twenty-one stakeholders answered all questions. Stakeholders agreed on including all 61 quality criteria rated as “relevant” or “very relevant” in round 2. Additionally, stakeholders agreed on the relevance of the criterion “nuclear medicine specialists” as a representative in the MDT, rated as “relevant” or “very relevant” by 71 % of stakeholders in round 2. Finally, 62 quality criteria for paediatric oncology centres in Switzerland were rated “relevant” and form the final list (Table 2, Supplemental material 3, Supplemental Table S4).

Some stakeholders commented on aspects that should be considered when implementing the quality criteria (Supplemental Table S5). A frequent comment was that terms used within quality criteria and their meaning need to be clearly defined (e.g., “collaboration”, “access to”, or “MDT”).

4. Discussion

4.1. Statement of principal findings

This study provides a comprehensive list of 62 quality criteria divided into six categories agreed on as relevant for paediatric oncology centres in Switzerland. All categories and most quality criteria identified in the international literature of countries with highly developed healthcare systems (Schladerer et al., 2023) were rated as relevant by the participating stakeholders.

4.2. Interpretation within the context of the wider literature

The applied method, a stakeholder consensus-finding process, has been used by other authors to define and prioritise quality measures in paediatric oncology. Similar approaches were used to define quality criteria for the paediatric oncology system (Bradley et al., 2013), the outpatient setting in paediatric oncology care (Teichman et al., 2017), and for adolescent and young adult cancer care (Rae et al., 2020) in Canada, and for end-of-life care of paediatric oncology patients in the US (Johnston et al., 2021). Many of these consensus processes were also based on literature searches and expert consultations.

In Europe, paediatric cancer centres in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland can get certified by OnkoZert, an independent institute in Germany that conducts certifications on behalf of the DKG (OnkoZert). To obtain the certification, centres need to fulfil predefined quality criteria. While their quality criteria focus mainly on numbers (e.g., number of patients introduced in an interdisciplinary tumour conference, number of patients that received a specific treatment) (Deutsche Krebsgesellschaft, 2024a), ours do not prioritise quantitative measures but cover holistic care provision.

4.3. Implications for policy, practice and research

Translating these evidence-based quality criteria into practice could enhance transparency and, thus, the quality of care within paediatric oncology centres. As we contacted stakeholders from different parts of Switzerland, this list of quality criteria will apply to centres throughout the country. However, its application is not limited to Switzerland as it is based on international evidence. It could be translated into the international context and implemented in countries with similar healthcare systems. The translation into the international context could be

Fig. 1. Results of round 1: Stakeholders consensus on the relevance of categories of quality criteria (answers to the question “Is the following category relevant?”).

Table 2

Results of round 2 & 3: Stakeholders' relevance ratings of quality criteria of relevant categories, and agreement decisions.

Quality criteria	ROUND 2 (N = 23)			ROUND 3 (N = 24)			
	n _{rel&very rel} / n _{rated} (%) ^a	Cannot assess n	Dropout n	n _{rel&very rel} / n _{rated} (%) ^{a,b}	Agreement inclusion n _{agreed} / n _{rated} ^{a,c}	Cannot assess n	Dropout n
FACILITIES, NETWORKS AND DISCIPLINES							
Included:							
1. National and international collaboration (e.g., through SSPHO, SPOG, SIOPE)	23/23 (100)	-	-		23/24 (100)	1	-
Access to:							
2. Pharmacy	19/20 (95)	3	-		21/24 (91)	1	-
3. Microbiology	17/19 (90)	4	-				
4. Laboratories (haematology, clinical chemistry)	22/22 (100)	1	-				
5. Transfusion service	20/20 (100)	3	-				
6. Pathology	22/23 (96)	-	-				
7. Fertility service	20/22 (91)	1	-				
8. Nuclear medicine	19/20 (95)	3	-				
9. Infectious diseases	21/22 (96)	1	-				
10. Radiation therapy	21/22 (96)	1	-				
Access to paediatric disciplines, including:							
11. Anaesthesia	21/21 (100)	2	-		20/23 (87)	-	1
12. Cardiology	21/21 (100)	2	-				
13. Intensive care unit	20/22 (91)	1	-				
14. Nephrology	18/20 (90)	3	-				
15. Neurosurgery	20/22 (91)	1	-				
16. Radiology	22/22 (100)	1	-				
17. Stem cell transplant unit	16/21 (76)	2	-				
18. Surgery with its sub-specialties (e.g. urology)	18/21 (86)	2	-				
19. Orthopaedics	16/20 (80)	3	-				
Excluded:							
Access to:							
Adult haematology and oncology	13/20 (65)	3	-	15/23 (65)		1	-
MULTIDISCIPLINARY TEAM (MDT) AND OTHER EXPERTS							
Included:							
20. MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences	21/21 (100)	2	-		22/23 (96)	-	1
Representatives/experts an MDT should consist of (depending on the patients' needs) - paediatric disciplines^d:							
21. Lead MDT	21/21 (100)	1	1		19/22 (91)	1	2
22. Neurologists	16/21 (76)	1	1				
23. Oncologists	22/22 (100)	-	1				
24. Oncology nurses	21/22 (96)	-	1				
25. Pathologists	20/21 (95)	1	1				
26. Radiologists	20/21 (95)	1	1				
27. Surgeons	20/22 (91)	-	1				
Representatives/experts an MDT should consist of (depending on the patients' needs)^d:							
28. Genetic specialists	19/22 (86)	-	1		17/22 (81)	1	2
29. Pain management experts	18/21 (86)	1	1				
30. Palliative care specialists	20/22 (91)	-	1				
31. Pharmacists experienced in chemotherapy preparation	16/21 (76)	1	1				
32. Psychosocial care/services incl. spiritual care and neuropsychological service	19/21 (91)	1	1				
33. Radiation oncologists	21/22 (96)	-	1				
34. Nuclear medicine specialists	15/21 (71)	1	1	16/21 (76)		1	2
Excluded:							
Minimal number of MDT members per patient volume	12/18 (67)	5	-	12/18 (67)		5	1
Representatives/experts an MDT should consist of (depending on the patients' needs) - paediatric disciplines:							
Anaesthesiologists	11/20 (55)	2	1	8/20 (40)		2	2
Cardiologists	11/19 (58)	3	1	8/21 (38)		1	2
Critical care specialists	11/19 (58)	3	1	10/21 (48)		1	2
Dermatologists	6/19 (32)	3	1	5/20 (25)		2	2
Endocrinologists	10/19 (54)	3	1	12/21 (57)		1	2
Gastroenterologists	8/18 (44)	4	1	7/20 (35)		2	2
Infectious diseases specialists	13/19 (68)	3	1	11/20 (55)		2	2
Nephrologists	10/18 (56)	4	1	10/21 (48)		1	2
Physiotherapists	10/19 (53)	3	1	10/20 (50)		2	2
Pulmonologists	6/18 (33)	4	1	6/20 (30)		2	2
Representatives/experts an MDT should consist of (depending on the patients' needs):							
Activity/play therapy staff	15/22 (68)	-	1	11/21 (52)		1	2
Complementary and alternative therapies	12/21 (57)	1	1	9/21 (43)		1	2
Dentists	8/21 (38)	1	1	9/21 (43)		1	2
Dieticians	15/21 (71)	1	1	11/21 (52)		1	2
Ear-nose-throat specialists	11/21 (52)	1	1	10/21 (48)		1	2
Laboratory technicians	12/21 (57)	1	1	10/21 (48)		1	2
Data managers	15/21 (71)	1	1	11/21 (52)		1	2
Occupational therapists	8/20 (40)	2	1	10/21 (48)		1	2
Ophthalmologists	9/20 (45)	2	1	11/21 (52)		1	2

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

	ROUND 2 (N = 23)			ROUND 3 (N = 24)		
Rehabilitation specialists	15/21 (71)	1	1	12/21 (57)	1	2
Ward teachers	13/21 (62)	1	1	13/21 (62)	1	2
SUPPORTIVE CARE						
SUPPORTIVE CARE & GUIDELINES						
Included:						
35. Availability of supportive care guidelines	19/21 (91)	1	1	21/22 (96)	-	2
The following supportive care should exist (including guidelines for it):						
36. Nausea and vomiting	21/21 (100)	1	1	21/22 (96)	-	2
37. Bowel disturbance	17/20 (85)	2	1			
38. Nutritional assessment	20/21 (95)	1	1			
39. Fertility (preservation)	22/22 (100)	-	1			
40. Pain relief (including local protocol for pain relief during procedures and adequate pain management)	19/21 (91)	1	1			
41. Palliative care (including bereavement)	21/22 (96)	-	1			
42. Psychological care	21/22 (96)	-	1			
43. Social care	22/22 (100)	-	1			
44. (Neuro-) rehabilitation	16/21 (76)	1	1			
45. Social care	21/22 (96)	-	1			
46. School education	17/21 (77)	-	1			
47. Cancer education	18/22 (82)	-	1			
Excluded:						
The following supportive care should exist (including guidelines for it):						
Dental care	11/22 (55)	2	1	11/20 (55)	2	2
SUPPORTIVE CARE: CENTRAL VENOUS CATHETER (CVC)						
Included:						
48. Complication rates: incidence of CVC-associated infection and surgical complication rates	16/19 (84)	3	1	19/20 (95)	1	3
49. Written policies/ procedures for the management of CVC	15/19 (79)	3	1	19/19 (100)	2	3
SUPPORTIVE CARE: FEBRILE NEUTROPENIA (F&N)						
Included:						
50. Guidelines on how to approach a child with F&N (availability, risk-stratified approach, escalation for fever persistence)	20/20 (100)	2	1	19/19 (100)	2	3
51. Number/Proportion of clinical F&N episodes in which the patients with or without microbial focus are treated with first line antibiotics according to local guidelines	14/17 (82)	5	1	15/18 (83)	3	3
52. Number/proportion of clinical F&N episodes in which the patient died	13/17 (77)	5	1	16/18 (89)	3	3
53. Number/Proportion of fungal associated infections	15/18 (83)	4	1	16/18 (89)	3	3
54. Time to antibiotic administration	17/18 (94)	4	1	17/19 (90)	2	3
Excluded:						
Number/proportion of clinical F&N episodes in which patients are admitted to ICU	12/17 (71)	5	1	11 (61)	3	3
TREATMENT						
Included:						
55. Number/Proportion of patients presented in the interdisciplinary tumour conference (for solid and liquid tumours separately or combined), including its documentation	19/21 (91)	1	1	18/21 (86)	-	3
56. Protocol compliance (e.g., number of major clinical trial protocol violations)	20/22 (91)	-	1	17/21 (81)	-	3
57. Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation	17/22 (77)	-	1	16/20 (80)	1	3
Excluded:						
Number/Proportion of failure to complete treatment	12/20 (60)	2	1	12/19 (63)	2	3
Number/Proportion of refusal to complete treatment	11/20 (55)	2	1	12/19 (63)	2	3
Diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) strategy for patients with special needs (e.g., due to migration, autism spectrum disorder/ neurodevelopment)	13/20 (65)	2	1	12/20 (60)	1	3
TREATMENT: MEDICATION						
Included:						
58. Number/proportion of patient safety incidents related to chemotherapy prescriptions	18/20 (90)	1	2	19/21 (91)	-	3
59. Number/proportion of actual or potential drug or dose errors identified for patients on active treatment	20/20 (100)	1	2	18/21 (86)	-	3
Excluded:						
Number/Proportion of elective paediatric oncology ambulatory procedures requiring anaesthesia that are deferred to the next day or beyond due to resource limitation(s)	10/17 (59)	4	2	6/17 (35)	4	3
LONG-TERM CARE						
Included:						
60. Number/Proportion of survivors of childhood cancer with a survivor care plan	17/20 (85)	1	2	20/21 (95)	-	3
61. Established follow-up and transition structure	19/21 (91)	-	2	21/21 (100)	-	3
VOLUME AND NUMBERS						
Included:						
62. Number of cases/clinic/year	17/20 (85)	1	2	19/20 (95)	1	3

Abbreviations: SSPHO, Swiss Society of Pediatric Hematology and Oncology; SPOG, Swiss Paediatric Oncology Group; SIOPE, European Society for Paediatric Oncology; MDT, multidisciplinary team; CVC, central venous catheter; F&N, febrile neutropenia; ICU, intensive care unit; DEI, diversity, equity, and inclusion

^a Cannot assess responses excluded from the calculation of percentage

^b Questions on re-rating were only asked for quality criteria that were rated as relevant & very relevant by < 75 % of stakeholders in round 2

^c Questions on agreement were only asked for quality criteria that were rated as relevant & very relevant by ≥ 75 % of stakeholders in round 2

^d List is not exhaustive, and additional disciplines may be required depending on each individual patient

coordinated through the International Society of Paediatric Oncology (SIOP) and its regional branches. While SIOP can propose and define standards, inform its members about quality criteria, and assist with implementation, the concrete realisation and monitoring of these quality criteria will need to be carried out at national or local levels.

Before implementing these quality criteria in centres or other countries, piloting them in one or a few pilot centres and countries is crucial. It could provide insights into aspects that should be adapted before widespread implementation, including, for example, how compliance with the criteria will be monitored. Besides, precise definitions must be established, including the terms used. For example, stakeholders advised that there should be a distinction between “active collaboration” and “passive collaboration” as well as “national collaboration” and “international collaboration” when defining the term “collaboration”. When referring to “access to” disciplines or treatment facilities, it should be clear whether the criterion refers to access within the centre, national, or international. As stakeholders often agreed with our list of MDT members, but stated that some other disciplines were relevant too, it needs to be declared that the list of the required MDT members is not exhaustive, but the composition of the MDT depends on the needs of each individual patient. Defining accurate and evidence-based thresholds can be challenging for some quality criteria. In this survey, many stakeholders stated that the number of cases/clinic/year is a political issue and that defining a threshold will be challenging. As the literature reports different threshold values, e.g., 5 cases/clinic/year (Knops et al., 2013) or 30 cases/clinic/year (European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE) et al., 2009), and it is unclear on what evidence these values are based on, these concerns are reasonable. Divergent statements on this criterion, such as that this “depends on the complexity of the treatment” versus “more cases result in more experience and knowledge”, show the variety among stakeholders’ opinions. When defining thresholds, it is essential to consider good clinical and ethical practices and legal regulations. One stakeholder commented on the criterion “Number/Proportion of patients presented in the interdisciplinary tumour conference (...), including its documentation” that this number could be inflated, might depend on the time availability of the tumour board participants, and is therefore not representative of the volume. However, this criterion refers to the mandatory discussion of all primary cases, which should not be related to the tumour board participants. The importance of multidisciplinary discussions is reflected by the comments of other stakeholders on the excluded criterion “Minimal number of MDT members per patient volume”. Stakeholders stated that the number of MDT participants is less relevant than their qualifications and specialities and that it is most important that discussions occur.

Overall, threshold values for some criteria may be derived from a combination of expert experiences and the international literature and adapted to the Swiss context. Further research, e.g., observational studies, stakeholder dialogues and further consensus-finding processes, may be needed to define appropriate thresholds for other quality criteria.

External quality assessment institutions need to be established, or collaboration with existing ones should be set up to implement quality criteria and regularly monitor their fulfilment. While the SPOG regularly monitors the SPOG centres regarding protocol compliance and clinical trails (Swiss Paediatric Oncology Group (SPOG), 2023), an independent institution should control the fulfilment of quality criteria. An example of such an institution is OnkoZert (OnkoZert) in Germany, which is part of the DKG, but an individual institution that carries out centre certification.

Surveillance of the fulfilment of these quality criteria is relevant and can enhance the quality of care provided nationally and internationally. The extent of fulfilment can be an orientation for different stakeholders and help identify and address shortcomings. Once carried out, future research could focus on the effectiveness of implementing these quality criteria by assessing improvements in the quality of care related to the extent of fulfilment of these quality criteria. The current quality criteria should be periodically reviewed through stakeholder dialogues and surveys.

4.4. Strengths and limitations

Through the survey-based online consensus-finding process, the exchange among stakeholders was limited and resulted in summarised survey results of all stakeholders. However, through the online realisation, we could involve numerous stakeholders, and we ensured that everyone would be “heard” as each stakeholder could respond to the same questions, and responses were collected.

The co-creation approach is a major strength of this study, involving stakeholders from the clinical setting, employees from the SPOG Coordinating Center, advocacy organisations, and survivor representatives. By building a consensus on evidence from international publications, we synthesised a list of quality criteria relevant to paediatric oncology centres in Switzerland by bringing together evidence from global research and views from national paediatric oncology practice and patient experience. We avoided a possible response and social-desirability bias by making the survey participation anonymous. The moderately high RRs of 35–45 % within three consecutive survey rounds among all language regions strengthen the representativeness of these results for the opinion across Switzerland.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study presents a list of evidence-based and stakeholder-agreed quality criteria that can be applied in Switzerland to assess the quality of care of paediatric oncology centres. While this list provides a foundation for further development, it is essential to note that clear thresholds and infrastructure still need to be established.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sarah Pia Schladerer: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maria Otth:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Katrin Scheinemann:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.ymecc.2024.100011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymecc.2024.100011).

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